

EVALUATION OF BORDERLINE PERSONALITY DISORDER AS A PREDICTOR OF DEVIANCE BEHAVIOUR AMONG STUDENTS OF BORSTAL TRAINING INSTITUTE KADUNA

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Abstract: This research examined Borderline Personality Disorder, gender differences and socioeconomic status as predictors of deviant behaviours among students of Borstal Training Institute. The age baseline for the assessment of borderline personality disorder is 18 years and for that reason, this study used, seventy six males (67.00%) and thirty seven (33.00%) females who were 18 years and above for the study. The participants were selected using purposive sampling technique. Three instruments were used; Demographic questionnaire, MacLean Screening Instrument for borderline personality disorder and Deviant Behaviour Variety Scale to collect data for the study while simple linear regression, t-test and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used in the analysis. The results showed that Borderline Personality Disorder predicted deviant behavior and there was a significant gender difference in deviant behavior among students of the Borstal Training Institute. There was no significant difference in deviant behaviour by socio-economic status among students of the Borstal Training Institute. Based on the result, the first and second alternate hypotheses were accepted while the third hypothesis was rejected. Limitations of the study were stated; and recommendations made for further studies.

Keywords: Borderline, Personality Disorder, Deviant Behaviours, Students and Borstal Training Institute.

1. INTRODUCTION

All over the world, deviance and criminality are socially fabricated. For example, in United States of America, homosexuality and gay marriage is considered normal, whereas in Nigeria, it is considered deviance. Deviance breeds crime and criminality, which in turn results in insecurities of both lives and properties. Nigeria has come to the point where majority of the people are concerned about insecurities in the country. Crime victims are no longer a question of affluence but of availability. Although Durkheim posited that crime serves useful functions in a society, there is always a limit to which a society can sustain crime, to avoid launching into a state of anomie. Through socialization, people learn that they must follow social norms and that failure to abide may result in unfavourable consequences, such as societal rejection, paying of fines, imprisonment and in extreme cases, incarceration and death penalty. Some people engage in criminal activities by socialization, triggered by the economic situation and the type of neighbourhood that they find themselves, this was similarly posited by Sampson (2012), who suggested that neighbourhoods with higher poverty rates tend to have higher rates of violent crime. The society's belief that youths are the leaders of tomorrow, make measures meted out on them for committing crime more of correctional than retributive and the quest to uphold fundamental human rights all over the world, gives a human face to the criminal justice system. Deviance and social norms go hand in hand. A norm is a cultural

expectation for behavior. Deviance is the nonconformity to a given set of norms that are accepted by a significant number of people in a community or society. Nonconformity refers to behaviors or ways of thinking that do not comply with social norms. According to Durkheim (1893), deviance is an integral part of a progressive society. One-way deviance is useful, he posited, is that it challenges people's present views (Durkheim, 1893). For instance, when black students across the United States participated in sit-ins during the civil rights movement, they challenged society's notions of segregation. More so, Durkheim noted, when deviance is punished, it reaffirms currently held social norms, which also contributes to society (1893). Seeing a student given detention for skipping class reminds other high schoolers that truancy is not allowed and that they, too, could get detention. Robert Merton, a sociologist, supported Durkheim's idea of the usefulness of deviance and added that, access to socially acceptable goals plays a part in determining whether a person conforms or deviates. Sociologists view deviance as behaviours that violates established rules and norms. This view is simply more than nonconformity, it entails behaviour that departs markedly from social expectations. Furthermore, they recognize that established rules and norms are socially created, not just morally decided or individually imposed. In other words, deviance lies not just in the behaviour itself, but in the social responses of groups to behaviour by others. Some types and examples of deviant behaviours in many societies include: armed robbery, murder, examination mal-practice, rape, forgery, drug abuse and addiction (smoking and drinking), bribery and corruption, homo-sexuality, vandalization, gangsterism, intimidating behaviours, keeping late hours, sexual harassment and indecent dressing (such as transparent and tied cloths for girls, and radical wears or appearance like coiling of hairs for boys), disobedience to parents, elders, and other social authorities, addicted to partying, gossiping, greed, jealousy, truancy, among others. On the other hand, Psychological perspective to deviance emphasized criminal tendency or deviance as natural human drives and urges that are repressed in the unconscious through the process of socialization (Nalah & Ishaya, 2013). The inappropriate organization of instinctual drive develops a personality disorder that implicates both personal (behavioural and intrapsychic) and social (interpersonal, group, macrosocial) structure and process. Personality is an individual's unique pattern of thoughts and behaviour. Even though an individual's personality stays the same over time, it is influenced by experiences, heredity and environment. Personality disorder is an inflexible pattern of inward experience and outward behaviour that deviates strongly from the expectations of the individual's culture, at least two or more of the following areas affected: cognition, affectivity, interpersonal functioning and impulse control (Comer, 2013). There are ten specific types of personality disorders according to DSM IV (TR), distributed into three clusters of A, B and C. Cluster B, of which Borderline Personality Disorder is a part of, has been linked to crime. Borderline Personality Disorder is characterized by a pattern of instability in personal relationships, intense emotions, poor self-image and impulsivity. An individual with borderline personality disorder may go to great lengths to avoid being abandoned, have repeated suicide attempts, display inappropriate intense anger or have ongoing feelings of emptiness. Borderline personality disorder is a complex disorder and it is fast becoming one of the more common conditions seen in clinical practice (Comer, 2013). Their impulsive self-destructive activities may range from alcohol and substance abuse to delinquency, unsafe sex and reckless driving (Coffey, Schumacher, Baschnagel, Hawk & Hollman, 2011; Sherry & Whilde, 2008). Personality disorders are among the most difficult psychological disorders to treat, and given the propensity of cluster B personality disorders to engage in crime, this study explores the relationship that exists between borderline personality disorder and deviance among inmates of Borstal Training Institute, Kaduna, state.

Statement of the problem

In a world of growing interdependence, crimes are no longer confined by national boundaries. Each country of the world is faced with a teeming increase in lives and property crimes. In the 2021 record of crimes index all over the world, Venezuela ranked first in criminality with a crime index of 83.76, followed by Papua New Guinea with a crime index of 80.79 and South Africa ranking third with a crime index of 76.86. Nigeria ranked sixteenth with a crime rate of 64.06 and Qatar being the least country with criminal activities had a crime rate of 12.13. The current upsurge of criminal activities, especially kidnappings and thefts, seemed under reported, or no proper records of crime are been kept or perhaps the method used in generating the indices for crime rate is favourable to Nigeria because of the population size of the country. Crime and criminality stem from deviance. Nigeria is saddled with a myriad of socio-economic and political problems which are multifarious in nature (Ibrahim, Odoh, Charlton, Gbenga, & Garba, 2020). These problems include corruption, poverty, nepotism, federal character, immorality, and social vices like deviance and crime. Crime is a major social problem in Nigeria like any other countries of the world, though there might be differences in patterns and social context in predisposition to criminality. Crime is one of the greatest threats to human security and attracts concerted efforts in its control especially through designated agencies like the police and so on. Aside the social concern of feeding, clothing and shelter, crime is a major concern of the Nigerian public. Concern and fear of crime among Nigerians is reflected in coping strategies such as living in houses with high walls similar to those of prisons, (Dambazau, 1994, Nwosu, 2001), formation of neighbourhood security association (vigilante), engaging private security guards and purchasing electronic security gadgets among other

strategies to protect themselves from falling victims of crime. Despite societal displeasure at the rate at which crime increases in Nigeria, little has been done to curb its excesses. In an exclusive interview with the Nigerian Television Authority on the 11th of June, 2021, the current president of Nigeria, Buhari emphasised that the major problem of the country is insecurity and as a result, no vacancy exists anywhere in the government parastatals for the teeming graduates, regardless of grades graduated with and school graduated from, this statement would be said to encourage deviance and hence criminality, as some youths resort to crimes to meet their everyday needs. Nigeria has been included among the countries with the least peace in the world, according to the Global Peace Index. Nationwide, crimes against property and persons are the most numerous types of offences reported to the police. According to statistics, one hundred and thirty-five thousand crimes were reported in Nigeria consisting of sixty-eight thousand, six hundred cases of property crimes, fifty-three thousand six hundred cases of crimes against persons and twelve thousand seven hundred cases of crimes against lawful authority in Nigeria (Simona, 2021). Five years records of major crimes in Kaduna state, spanning 2015-2020, generated from Kaduna state CID, showed that there were three hundred and seventy five recorded cases of armed robbery, six hundred and seventy three cases of murder, six hundred and sixty one cases of rape, two hundred and ninety one cases of assault and two hundred and eighty five cases of kidnapping. Many factors have been attributed to the rising insecurity in the country, could personality disorder be one of them? Personality disorder is a pattern of personality that has met the criteria for mal- adaptiveness and clinical significance. Clinicians have long been aware of associations between mental illness and criminality. Indeed, according to a recent report by 57 independent monitoring boards of prisons in the United Kingdom (UK), 90 percent of inmates have at least one diagnosable mental disorder. Some sociologists theorized that deviant behaviour can be learnt by so many ways during socialization. Could it be that personality disorders are birthed as a result of constantly seeking avenues to meet social expectations? The prevalence of borderline personality disorder, in the general US population ranges between two percent with rates reportedly greater in women (i.e., the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fourth Edition, Text Revision*) and six percent with rates approximately equal between the sexes (Grant, Bredahl, Clay, Ferrie, Groves, Hirman, & Dark, 1998). Few researches have been carried out with regards to borderline personality disorder and deviance, hence criminality. Sansome and Sansome, (2009), carried out a research on borderline personality and criminality and found that borderline personality disorder is characteristically associated with a broad variety of psychiatric symptoms and aberrant behaviors. According to their review of literature, in comparison with the rates of borderline personality disorder encountered in the general population, borderline personality disorder is over-represented in most studies of inmates. At the same time, there is considerable variation in the reported rates of this Axis II disorder in prison populations, which may be attributed to the methodologies of and populations in the various studies. Overall, female criminals appear to exhibit higher rates of borderline personality disorder, and it is oftentimes associated with a history of childhood sexual abuse, perpetration of impulsive and violent crimes, comorbid antisocial traits, and incarceration for domestic violence (Sansome & Sansome, 2009). Another study by Gonzalez, Igoumenou, Kallis and Coid (2016), on Borderline Personality Disorder and Violence in the UK population, found that Borderline Personality Disorder is associated with Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) and associations with serious violence leading to injuries and repetitive violence were better explained by comorbid substance misuse, anxiety and antisocial personality disorder (ASPD). Davison and Aleksandar (2012) researched on personality disorder and criminal behaviour. They looked at the relationship between cluster B personality disorders and patterns of criminality and violence in a sample of women incarcerated in a maximum secured correctional center and found no relationship between anti-social, borderline, histrionic, or narcissistic personality disorder scores and history of convictions, apart from a negative relationship between anti-social personality disorder scores and homicide and a positive relationship between borderline personality disorder scores and prostitution. Unfortunately, no such records exist in Nigeria. The major goal of the institute is to remand and give both educational and vocational training to juvenile offenders between the ages of 16 to 21, so as to make them better citizens instead of being potential threat to the country. This training which lasts for three years, sees to the juvenile offenders' modification of social behaviour through guardian and counseling, assessment of circumstances leading to delinquent behaviour, vocational training, medical services, chaplaincy services, preventive health services among others.

Objectives of the study

The general aim of the study is to evaluate borderline personality disorder as a predictor of deviance among students of Borstal Training Institute, Kaduna state. Specifically, the study sought to examine:

- i. The extent to which Borderline personality disorder will predict deviance amongst students of Borstal Training Institute.
- ii. Socio economic status difference in exhibition of deviance amongst students of Borstal Training Institution with borderline personality disorder.

2. METHODS

Design

This study employed the survey research design to evaluate borderline personality disorder as predictive of deviance among students of Borstal training institute. Survey research design is the process of conducting research using survey questionnaires that research participants respond to. The independent variable of the study was borderline personality disorder, while the dependent variable was deviance, however, demographic variables such as gender and socio-economic status were also studied to see how they contribute to deviance. This design was used because no variables were manipulated, and only information already present in the population was recorded.

Participants

This study was conducted using students of Borstal Training Institute Kaduna. The general population of the students was two hundred and fifty-six (n=256), consisting of all males and females. The baseline for the assessment of borderline personality disorder is 18 years and for that reason, this study was conducted with all the males who were 18 years and above as at the time of the study. The age of the participants ranged from 18 to 21 years with a mean age of 19.34 (SD=1.07).

Sample Size/Sampling Technique

The sampling technique employed was purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique in which researchers rely on their own judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in their surveys. The population of students in Borstal Training Institute is 256, with a composition of 226 males and 26 females. Out of this population, a total of one hundred and sixteen 116 males were selected for the purpose of this study, using 18 years as the baseline for this selection. Purposive sampling technique was adopted since the researcher expected the participants to meet certain requirement as was stated above.

Instrument

The instrument used for data collection, consists of three sections: section A made provisions for demographic variables studied (gender and socioeconomic status).

Section B contained the scale on deviance. Deviance was measured using Deviant Behaviour Variety Scale, developed by Sanches, Gouvela-Pereira, Maroco, Gomes, and Roncon (2016). The scale includes both illegal behavior and rule-breaking behavior that is not illegal (e.g. lying to adults, or skipping school for several days without parental consent). The scale contains 19 items (e.g. During The Last Year, Have You Ever..... Lied to adults (e.g., family members, teachers, etc.); Used cocaine or heroin? Etc.) answered using a five-point Likert scale (0= never to 4= Always), regarding whether the participants have engaged in each of the 19 behaviors during the previous year (6month DVB). The total score for deviant behaviors is obtained by the sum of positive answers. The participants were also asked to write the number of behaviors they had engaged in throughout their entire life (Lifelong DVB). The coefficient level of deviant behaviour variety scale is 0.70.

Section C, contained the scale on borderline personality disorder. Borderline personality disorder was measured in this study using MacLean Screening Instrument for borderline personality disorder, developed by Zanarini & Mary (2003). The MSI-BPD consists of 10 items, (e.g. "Have any of your closest relationships been troubled by a lot of arguments or repeated breakups? Have you often felt that you had no idea of who you are or that you have no identity?") answered using a five-point Likert scale (0= never to 4= Always), with the sum score providing an indication of BPD symptomatology. Scores of 28 or more is indicative of BPD (Zanarini et al., 2003). Preliminary data using non-patients only indicated that MSI-BPD assesses a single construct, and has adequate internal consistency ($\alpha = .76$), and a high 4-month test-retest reliability ($r = .80$) (Verschuere & Tibboel, 2011).

Data collection was conducted in one day. A total of 116 questionnaires were returned and properly filled.

Statistical Technique Used

The study used simple linear regression to test for the relationship between deviance and borderline personality disorder. The study used regression and ANOVA to test for socio-economic status (low class, middle class and high class) among students of Borstal Institute. The analysis was done using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21.

3. RESULTS

Presentation of Data

The result of data analysis is presented here with tables indicating different result of the findings.

Table 1: Means, Standard Deviations, and Correlations for Borderline Personality Disorder, Socioeconomic Status and Deviant Behaviour

S/N	Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4
1	Deviant_Beh	54.17	18.16	-	.33***	.18*	-.61***
2	BPD	29.94	12.69		-	.02	-.11
3	SES	1.88	.83			.	-

*= P <.05; **=p<.01; ***=p<.001(significant)

Result of correlation table show that deviant behaviour was significantly related to Borderline Personality Disorder (r = .33, p < .001) and socioeconomic status (r = -.61, p < .001).

Hypotheses one: Borderline personality disorder will significantly predict deviance among students of Borstal Training Institute.

Table 2: Regression analysis for borderline personality disorder and deviance among students of Borstal Training Institute.

Coefficients ^a							
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	12.593	.429		29.350	.001	10.747	14.439
BPD	.027	.133	.059	.203	.034	-.546	.600

a. Dependent Variable: Deviance

$$\text{Deviance} = a_0 + a_1\text{BPD}$$

$$\text{Deviance} = 12.593 + 0.027\text{BPD}$$

$$F\text{-Stat.} = 21.704$$

$$R^2 = 0.970$$

$$R^2 = 0.925$$

$$D\text{-W} = -2.853$$

The coefficient of the constant is 12.665. It implies that when the independent variables are held constant, the value of the deviant behaviour will be 12.593.

Borderline personality disorder (BPD) shows a positive value of 0.027, implying that one per cent increase in the borderline personality disorder causes the deviant behaviour to increase by 0.027 per cent.

From the t-table, the theoretical t-value at 5% level of significance. Since the theoretical t-value is less than the absolute values of the calculated t-values for the entire parameter estimates i.e Borderline Personality Disorder, we shall therefore reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. This implies that the parameter estimates are statistically different from zero i.e. they are relevant variables in the prediction of the deviant behaviour.

The coefficient of determination gives 0.970 or 97.0% meaning that the regression model is approximately 97% significant i.e the variations in the dependent variable i.e. deviance is 97% attributable to the changes in the independent variable i.e exchange rate fluctuation, interest rate and inflation rate borderline personality disorder. This result is also supported by the high value of the adjusted R-Square, which is to the tune of 92.5%

The theoretical F-value at 5% level of significance with 19.16. Since the calculated F-value (21.704) is greater than the critical value, we shall reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. This signifies that the overall regression or relationship between the deviance and borderline personality disorder is significant. So, the changes in the deviance can be attributed to changes in the explanatory variable i.e borderline personality disorder. Therefore, this analysis revealed that borderline personality significantly predicts deviance among students of Borstal Training Institute.

Hypothesis Two: There will be statistically difference in deviance by socio-economic status among students of Borstal Training Institute.

Table 3: Showing analysis of variance (ANOVA) for socio-economic status and deviance among students of Borstal Training Institute.

Source	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between Groups		5	10.756	1.493	0.204
SES	53.778				
Within groups		66	7.202		
SES	475.333				
Total	529.111	71			

Table 4.7 above shows the socio-economic status mean scores of respondents identified in Borstal Training Institute. The F value for socio-economic status scores is 1.493 and P-value of 0.204 was obtained which is higher than 0.05 alpha level of significant. This analysis shows that no significant difference exists among the groups (low class, middle class and high class).

This showed that the socio-economic status of the students did not reveal any difference in the student’s deviant behaviour. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant difference in deviance by socio-economic status among students of Borstal Training Institute was retained.

4. DISCUSSION

The study examined borderline personality disorder as a predictor of deviance among students of Bostal Training Institute, Kaduna. Test of Hypothesis one results revealed that borderline personality disorder significantly predicts deviance among students of Bostal Training Institute, Kaduna. This finding implies that students of the Bostal Training Institute who are diagnosed with borderline personality disorder are more likely to engage in deviant acts when compared to their counterparts who do not share the same diagnosis. The first hypothesis that Borderline personality disorder will not significantly predict deviance behaviour among students of Borstal Training Institute was not confirmed by this result; therefore, we rejected the null hypothesis. This result finds support from the results of several other studies carried out in the past. According to Conn, Warden, Stuewig, Kim, Harty, Hastings and Tangney (2010), Borderline personality disorder has been found to be predictive of criminal activity in women and men. Empirical evidence points to moderate comorbidity between borderline personality disorder and psychopathy in men's prison populations (Douglas et al., 2007; Stalenhein & von Knorring, 1996) as well as in female population (Hochhausen, Lorenz & Newman, 2002; Salekin, Rogers & Sewell, 1997). The deviant activities carried out by individuals diagnosed of Borderline personality disorder may range from alcohol and substance abuse to delinquency, unsafe sex and reckless driving (Coffey, Schumacher, Baschnagel, Hawk & Hollman, 2011; Sherry & Wihle, 2008). This result was also backed by the postulations of Linehan’s Biosocial Theory (Linehan, 1993). The biosocial theory posits that if children have inherent difficulty in identifying and controlling their emotions and if parents teach them to ignore their intense feelings, they may never learn to properly recognize and control their emotional arousal, how to tolerate emotional distress or when to trust their emotional responses (Herpertz & Bertsch, 2014; Lazarus et al., 2014; Gratz & Tull, 2011) which ultimately causes them to respond and react to situations in socially unacceptable manners.

The second hypothesis test results showed that socioeconomic status did not significantly predict deviance among students of Borstal Training Institute, Kaduna. Individuals with both low and high socioeconomic status did not significantly differ in deviant acts. The second hypothesis which stated that there will be a statistically significant economic class difference in exhibition of deviance amongst students of Bostal Training Institution with borderline personality disorder was rejected. A long history of research showing the elevated risk of adult antisocial personality disorder among the offspring of families in poverty has established this relationship (Brandt, 2006; Pagani, Boulerice, Vitaro, & Tremblay, 1999; Petras et al, 2004. Sampson (2012) posited that neighbourhoods with higher poverty rates tend to have higher rates of violent crime. This finding is not in congruent with the postulations of Agnew’s (1992) strain theory of deviance which posits that people

engage in criminal activities or deviant behaviours to escape strain or stress which is a gap between cultural goal and the means of achieving them. For example, people may steal to solve a financial need or run away from home and towns to escape abusive parents and relationships.

5. CONCLUSION

The present study used a survey design and revealed that Borderline personality disorder was a significant predictor of deviant behaviours among Borstal Correctional Students in Kaduna State. There is no Socio-economic difference among the participants. This finding implies that males are not differ in exhibiting deviance and also people diagnosed with borderline personality disorder are more likely to engage in deviant acts. Also, being of a lower class or upper socio-economic class does not predispose one to engaging in deviant acts.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following suggestions were made:

- i. Individuals showing early signs of disturbing deviant behaviours should be tested for borderline personality disorder so that he/she can get the help needed before internalizing deviance and criminal attitudes.
- ii. This study should be replicated in correctional centers across the country and also with larger sample sizes to see if results apply to other populations.
- iii. In addition to rehabilitation of deviant individuals, the Bostal correctional institute should also endeavor to give psychotherapy to those who may need it as research has shown that 90% of the prison population has at least one psychological disorder which may as well be the reason for their being there.
- iv. When looking for the motivation behind a crime or deviant act, law enforcement agents should not downplay the role of personality disorders as they have been established as predictors of deviant or criminal behaviours.

Implication of Findings

The findings of this study also have several practical implications for the Nigerian society. For a country battling to tackle the ever increasing rate of crime, identifying some of the major of the risk factors is a very huge step in the right direction. A problem cannot be properly solved if the possible causes are not identified. This study provides policy makers and the National Orientation Agency some of the places to look in a bid to tackle deviance and crime which includes personality disorders and poverty.

Policy makers can incorporate poverty alleviation programmes such as skill acquisition and grants in the fight against crime and deviance. Also, correctional centers can employ more forensic and clinical psychologists to also rehabilitate the minds of inmates even as they undergo a physical rehabilitation. This result is also important to parents who may think their children are possessed by evil spirits due to their continuous deviant behaviours, as they can now understand better the role of personality difference and disorders in deviant behaviours and consequently take timely and appropriate actions to get the child the help he/she needs.

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